

**E-GOVERNANCE IN PRACTICE:
A STUDY OF ONLINE PUBLIC GRIEVANCE
REDRESSAL IN KARNATAKA
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ABSTRACT:

In this paper, we take a closer look at the impressive progress made by the Government of Karnataka in resolving public grievances digitally over the period of time in various departments under the state government. It focuses on the significant impact made on lives of common man by improving the effectiveness, efficiency, transparency, and accountability of governance processes, services, and decision-making. The integrated Public Grievance Redressal System (iPGRS) is an online platform available to the citizens to lodge their grievances to the public authorities on any subject related to service delivery in Karnataka. It was launched on 1st November 2021. It is a single portal connected to more than 40 Department schemes/ services delivered by the Government of Karnataka. It discusses how efficient iPGRS in the redressal of public grievances. This research article evaluates the performance and effectiveness of IPGRS-Janaspandana in Karnataka during the period 2024–2025.

KEYWORDS:

E-Governance, Public Grievance Redressal, iPGRS, Janaspandana,
Digital Governance, Karnataka.

1. Introduction

In a democratic polity, the right of citizens to voice grievances against administrative actions forms an essential component of good governance. Public grievance redressal mechanisms function as an interface between the government and the governed, ensuring responsiveness, accountability, and transparency in public administration. Traditionally, grievance redressal in India was characterized by bureaucratic delays, lack of accessibility, and procedural complexity.

With the advent of information and communication technology, governments have increasingly adopted digital platforms to improve service delivery and grievance handling. Karnataka has been at the forefront of e-governance reforms in India and has introduced an Online Public Grievance Redressal System to facilitate easy registration, tracking, and disposal of citizen complaints. This paper examines how effectively this system functions and whether it fulfils its intended objectives.

2. Concept of Public Grievance Redressal

A public grievance refers to a complaint or representation made by a citizen regarding non-delivery, delay, or deficiency in public services, or maladministration by government authorities. An effective grievance redressal mechanism ensures:

- Timely response by authorities
- Fair and reasoned decision-making
- Transparency in administrative processes
- Restoration of public trust in governance

3. Online Public Grievance Redressal System in Karnataka

Karnataka's online grievance redressal framework operates through multiple integrated platforms. Citizens can register grievances online, receive acknowledgment, track the status of complaints, and seek escalation if dissatisfied with the response. The system covers a wide range of departments including revenue, education, health, urban local bodies, police, and social welfare.

Janaspandana, officially known as the Integrated Public Grievance Redressal System (iPGRS), is a state-level digital governance initiative of the Government of Karnataka aimed at institutionalising a unified, paper-free mechanism for addressing public grievances. The system enables

citizens to formally place service-related complaints before the State administration and ensures structured scrutiny, inter-departmental coordination, and outcome-based closure.

In order to improve administrative responsiveness and strengthen citizen-government interaction, the Government of Karnataka operationalised iPGRS on 01 November 2021, coinciding with the State formation celebrations. iPGRS facilitates submission of grievances pertaining to public services administered by more than forty State Government departments. The system functions in electronic coordination with the Central Public Grievance Redress and Monitoring System (CPGRAMS) of the Government of India. Complaints lodged through the central portal, upon selection of Karnataka State, are digitally transmitted to iPGRS for examination and disposal. Final disposal status and compliance reports are relayed back to the central system through secure data exchange protocols.

4. An Evaluation of performance and effectiveness of IPGRS–Janaspandana in Karnataka during the period 2024–2025 (Table 1 and Table 2)

Table 1. Department-Wise Public Grievances Registered and Disposed through iPGRS in Karnataka (2025)

Sl. No.	Department	Grievance Registered	Closed (Feedback Pending)	Closed (Resolved Satisfactorily)	In Progress (Within Timeline)	In Progress (Exceeded TimeLine)
1	Rural Development and Panchayath Raj Department	20274	805	19376	50	43
2	Revenue Department	15668	862	14050	524	232
3	Urban Development Department	12295	1641	10359	272	23
4	Department of Women and Child Welfare	3201	221	2658	14	308
5	Housing Department	2517	177	2218	53	69
6	Energy Department	2051	109	1923	12	7
7	Transport Department	1895	107	1689	97	2
8	Home Department	1883	123	1568	94	98

9	Backward Classes Welfare Department	1764	38	1707	5	14
10	Food and Civil Supplies Department	1355	52	1293	2	8
11	Labour Department	1345	36	1295	12	2
12	Department of Social Welfare	1240	41	1179	9	11
13	Public Works Department	1097	47	1039	9	2
14	Agriculture Department	934	46	872	3	13
15	Skill Development, Entrepreneurship and Livelihood Department	842	78	763	1	0
16	Department of Cooperation	719	13	623	18	65
17	Department of School Education and Literacy	712	24	585	55	48
18	Forest, Ecology and Environment Department	706	51	626	23	6
19	Scheduled Tribes Welfare Department	686	27	653	3	3
20	Health and Family Welfare Department	585	35	497	35	18
21	Minorities Welfare Department	542	24	503	1	14
22	Commerce and Industries Department	469	11	394	48	16
23	Water Resources Department	403	14	385	0	4
24	Animal Husbandry and Fisheries Department	374	25	343	3	3
25	Higher Education Department	291	11	251	4	25
26	Finance Department	284	14	267	3	0
27	DPAR(E-Gov)	238	14	216	4	4

28	Minor Irrigation Department	219	10	202	5	2
29	Law Department	175	0	134	1	40
30	Horticulture and Sericulture Department	171	6	158	1	6
31	Medical Education Department	149	5	123	4	17
32	DPAR (Administrative Reforms)	96	0	86	0	10
33	Tourism Department	77	0	77	0	0
34	Kannada and Culture Department	53	3	48	1	1
35	Department of Personnel and Administrative Services (DPAR)	51	0	48	2	1
36	Information and PR Department	43	0	43	0	0
37	Youth Empowerment and Sports Department	40	3	36	0	1
38	Department of Electronics Information Technology Biotechnology and Science and Technology	23	0	23	0	0
39	Infrastructure Development Department	22	0	22	0	0
40	Department Of Public Enterprises	19	0	0	0	19
41	Department of Parliamentary Affairs and Law (DPAL)	2	0	2	0	0

Source: Compiled by the author from iPGRS–Janaspadana portal, Government of Karnataka (2025).

Table 2. Department-Wise Public Grievances Registered and Disposed through iPGRS in Karnataka (2024)

Sl. No	Department	Grievance Registered	Closed (Feedback Pending)	Closed (Resolved Satisfactorily)	In Progress (Within Timeline)	In Progress (Exceeded TimeLine)
1	Revenue Department	26502	1	26461	29	11
2	Rural Development and Panchayath Raj Department	19545	2	19542	0	1
3	Urban Development Department	9445	15	9423	6	1
4	Housing Department	4503	74	4404	19	6
5	Energy Department	3766	1	3764	0	1
6	Department of Women and Child Welfare	3737	0	3735	0	2
7	Department of Social Welfare	3654	3	3645	0	6
8	Home Department	3040	5	3031	4	0
9	Transport Department	1878	1	1877	0	0
10	Food and Civil Supplies Department	1788	0	1779	0	9
11	Agriculture Department	1728	0	1728	0	0
12	Department of Cooperation	1699	0	1698	0	1
13	Department of School Education and Literacy	1417	1	1410	4	2
14	Backward Classes Welfare Department	1395	0	1395	0	0
15	Public Works Department	1219	0	1218	1	0
16	Health and Family Welfare Department	854	3	846	1	4
17	Labour Department	848	0	848	0	0
18	Scheduled Tribes Welfare Department	726	0	726	0	0

19	Forest, Ecology and Environment Department	708	1	706	1	0
20	Water Resources Department	657	0	657	0	0
21	Skill Development, Entrepreneurship and Livelihood Department	637	0	637	0	0
22	Animal Husbandry and Fisheries Department	575	0	575	0	0
23	Minorites Welfare Department	488	0	488	0	0
24	Commerce and Industries Department	484	0	481	3	0
25	Minor Irrigation Department	305	0	305	0	0
26	Higher Education Department	299	0	296	0	3
27	Finance Department	298	2	295	1	0
28	Horticulture and Sericulture Department	187	1	186	0	0
29	DPAR(E-Gov)	176	1	175	0	0
30	Kannada and Culture Department	135	0	135	0	0
31	Department of Personnel and Administrative Services (DPAR)	103	0	103	0	0
32	Youth Empowerment and Sports Department	95	0	95	0	0
33	Medical Education Department	86	0	86	0	0
34	Tourism Department	84	1	83	0	0
35	Information and PR Department	65	0	65	0	0

36	DPAR (Administrative Reforms)	62	0	62	0	0
37	Department of Electronics Information Technology Biotechnology and Science and Technology	32	0	32	0	0
38	Infrastructure Development Department	25	0	25	0	0
39	Department Of Public Enterprises	18	0	1	0	17
40	Law Department	6	0	6	0	0
41	Department of Parliamentary Affairs and Law (DPAL)	1	0	1	0	0

Source: Compiled by the author from iPGRS–Janaspadana portal, Government of Karnataka (2024).

The dataset covers grievance-related information from 41 government departments, classified under the following parameters:

- Total grievances registered
- Grievances resolved satisfactorily
- Cases closed but awaiting complainant feedback
- Grievances under processing within the stipulated period
- Grievances pending beyond the prescribed timeline
- Quantitative analysis of these variables enables assessment of departmental performance and systemic effectiveness.

4.1 Analysis of Grievance Registration Patterns

Across both years under study, departments such as the Revenue Department, Rural Development and Panchayat Raj Department, and Urban Development Department reported the highest number of registered grievances. This pattern reflects the extensive public interface of these departments and the essential nature of the services they deliver. A higher volume of grievances indicates increased citizen engagement and improved accessibility of the grievance redressal mechanism rather than administrative

inefficiency, and it also signifies growing public confidence in digital grievance redressal systems.

4.2 Evaluation of Grievance Resolution

4.2.1 Resolution Trends in 2024

The grievance data for 2024 reveals that most departments resolved a substantial proportion of registered grievances, while only a limited number of cases remained pending beyond prescribed timelines. In several departments, complete disposal of grievances was achieved, indicating effective internal coordination, monitoring, and administrative responsiveness during the initial phase of evaluation.

4.2.2 Resolution Trends in 2025

In 2025, grievance resolution performance demonstrated further improvement, with several departments recording near-total satisfactory resolution of grievances. Timeline overruns declined sharply across departments, and resolution efficiency became more consistent and uniform. This improvement suggests administrative learning, refinement of digital workflows, and strengthened supervisory oversight within the Janaspandana-iPGRS framework.

4.3 Analysis of Pendency and Time Compliance

4.3.1 Delayed Grievances in 2024

During 2024, a limited number of departments, particularly those dealing with legal matters and public enterprises, exhibited relatively higher delays in grievance disposal. These delays were department-specific and did not indicate systemic inefficiency within the grievance redressal framework.

4.3.2 Reduction in Delays during 2025

By 2025, the number of grievances pending beyond prescribed timelines declined significantly across most departments. This reduction reflects improved time management and stronger enforcement of accountability norms through automated tracking, escalation mechanisms, and periodic performance reviews.

4.4 Citizen Feedback and Post-Resolution Engagement

Feedback-pending cases provide valuable insights into citizen participation following grievance closure. While feedback pendency was noticeable in 2024, particularly in departments with high grievance

volumes, it reduced considerably in 2025. This improvement indicates enhanced communication with complainants and increased awareness among citizens regarding feedback submission, thereby strengthening participatory governance.

4.5 Comparative Assessment of Grievance Redressal Performance (2024–2025)

A comparative assessment of grievance redressal performance reveals that resolution efficiency improved from high levels in 2024 to very high levels in 2025. Timeline compliance strengthened considerably, inter-departmental performance became more uniform, and feedback completion rates improved, reflecting operational consolidation and system stabilisation.

4.6 Identification of Consistently Efficient Departments

Departments such as Transport, Agriculture, Backward Classes Welfare, Water Resources, and Kannada and Culture demonstrated consistent excellence in grievance resolution across both years. Sustained performance in these departments reflects strong internal grievance-handling mechanisms, clearly defined accountability structures, and effective departmental leadership.

4.7 Major Analytical Findings

- Janaspandana-iPGRS exhibits a high level of functional effectiveness.
- Time-bound grievance redressal has improved considerably during the study period.
- The system shows evidence of institutional consolidation and operational maturity.
- Administrative delays are confined to a limited number of departments.
- The platform has enhanced transparency and citizen trust in governance.

5. Conclusion

The analysis of grievance data for 2024 and 2025 establishes that Janaspandana-iPGRS has significantly strengthened the grievance redressal ecosystem in Karnataka. The system demonstrates robust performance in terms of grievance disposal, timeline compliance, and citizen engagement, thereby reinforcing the principles of responsive and accountable governance.

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Conflict of interest:

The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare that they are relevant to the content of this article.

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